

Instruction-Immersion-Interaction (3Is) Theory of English Language Proficiency in Secondary Education

KAREN E. ZULUETA

Ed. D – English Language Teaching
main.07015133@cnu.edu.ph

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Chapter 1 THEORY GENERATION

ABSTRACT

In secondary education, there is a gap between educators and learners in using English language as the medium of instruction, during language exposure and through interaction. To address these educational challenges, this study aimed to develop a theory on English language proficiency. The researcher utilized the deductive axiomatic approach of theory development by Padua (2012). These axioms are: (1) English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) is used in different countries, (2) Language instruction challenges students' English proficiency, (3) Immersion to English language is linked to students' language skills, (4) Learners' social interaction develops English communication, and (5) English language Instruction, Immersion and Interaction enhance English proficiency. The propositions are: (1) Implementing English as a medium of instruction in language classes addresses students' language skills, (2) Language exposure to diverse contexts develops learners' English language skills, and (3) Increased social interaction enhances learners' English language proficiency particularly in communication skills. The theory generated is Instruction-Immersion-Interaction (3Is) Theory of English Language Proficiency in Secondary Education where in 3Is is a non-sequential approach of teaching and learning English language that aims to develop learners' English language proficiency among secondary language learners.

Keywords: *English Language Proficiency, Language Exposure, Communication Skills, Social Interaction, Axiomatic Approach, Theory Development*

1 INTRODUCTION

2
3 English Language Proficiency is a critical component of a
4 successful modern society. Nealer and Runde (2017) accentuated that
5 English is the third most spoken and most widely taught language on
6 the planet. Commonly used in over 100 countries by more than 300
7 million people as a first language and by over 600 million as a second
8 language. English is a global language and the lingua franca of the
9 modern era. One of the strategic benefits to English proficiency is that
10 English is the language of education and research.
11

12 English Medium Instruction (EMI) is broadly defined as “the use
13 of the English language to teach academic subjects (other than English
14 itself) in countries or jurisdictions in which the majority of the
15 population’s first language is not English” (Macaro, 2020, p. 534).
16 English as a medium of instruction in global context has been used in
17 different countries. Smith (2015) strengthened this claim that English is
18 being learned to work and communicate in a rapidly expanding global
19 community where only one language is required. Numerous institutions
20 in the world use English as the language of instruction in different
21 classrooms. The period of teaching-learning process utilizing English
22 language has proven to have a good impact to learners’ language
23 performances. As Protacio (2023) stated though challenging to teach
24 and learn, English is a potent tool for education and proficiency where
25 teachers favored that English plays a significant role in the academe.
26

27 The Philippines is considered as one of the largest
28 Englishspeaking nations in the world. In fact, English is one of the
29 official languages in the Philippines (Fernandez, et al., 2022). In
30 Philippine educational system, English has been widely used in varied
31 learning areas where English language is suggested and applied in
32 both written and oral form of communication. Today's educators
33 confront the daunting task of meeting the requirements of an increasing
34 population of students whose first language is not English (Vizconde,
35 2006). The requirement for non-native speakers, like the Filipinos, to
36 be skilled in the usage of English has indeed become a worldwide
37 phenomenon. So, in order to teach the subject contents in non-English
38 country, the teachers need English as a language of instruction.
39

40 English is the official language in education. It is mandated in
41 Section 7 of Article XIV of the 1987 Philippine Constitution and
42 Executive Order No. 210: Establishing a policy to strengthen the use of
43 English as the official Language of Instruction (LOI) in the Philippine
44 educational system (Office of the President of the Philippines, May 17,
45 2003, Supreme Court E-Library). With this, teachers are designing and
46 conducting English classes to enhance students' language skills.
47 Educational institutions are focused on raising the standard of English
48 language instruction. Curriculum developers are creating new and
49 innovative materials for English proficiency.

50
51 In secondary education, English language teachers use English
52 as the medium of instruction during the actual teaching hours. However,
53 this is not all throughout the class period as far as the grammar
54 translation approach is concerned to cater students' diverse levels –
55 basically their skills and needs. This is supported by Protacio (2023)
56 emphasizing that teachers have acknowledged that English can be
57 supplemented by Filipino language and to some extent, native tongues
58 to assure comprehension of the subject matter.

59
60 On the other hand, most learners found it challenging to use
61 English language inclusively within the duration of English class.
62 Hence, learners' weaknesses in comprehending English as the medium
63 of instruction affect them in communicating or expressing their ideas
64 using English. This is affirmed by Manh (2012) stating that when the
65 students have low English proficiency, it is difficult for them to
66 understand the materials that are explained to them. With this, there is
67 a contrasting approach between the teachers' proficiency in delivering
68 English language and the learners' difficulty in utilizing English as it is
69 the medium of instruction in language classes.

70
71 There is a gap between educators and learners in using English
72 language as the medium of instruction in English classes. The teachers'
73 expertise and learners' difficulty in dealing with English as a medium of
74 instruction is one of the prevalent educational challenges that needs to
75 be addressed in secondary education. This gap comprises the technical
76 vocabulary used by the teachers in delivering instructions and within
77 the contexts of language embedded in activities and assessment where
78 learners are not familiar of or worse no knowledge about resulting to
79 their difficulty of analyzing the language. Second, the teacher

80 proficiency as it is a concern by the learners that the more they find the
81 teachers expert in using the English language, the more the learners
82 struggle in their comprehension. Third, codeswitching diversity where
83 some teachers deliver the instruction in a manner of switching one
84 language to another that led to students demonstrating similarly as how
85 the language is used by the teachers. The very limited access to
86 English as the target language with classroom instruction has been
87 seen as determinant of the slow learning rate observed in typical
88 classroom settings (Muñoz, 2006).

89
90 There is also a gap in the quality of learners' language exposure
91 in diverse contexts through the utilization of English as the medium of
92 instruction. As emphasized by Cadierno and Muñoz (2021), the amount
93 of English instruction that learners are exposed to in school is one of
94 the factors of the notable differences in English proficiency levels
95 across geographical contexts. An insufficient exposure to the target
96 language can be influenced by the learner's anxiety and self-efficacy,
97 mainly in speaking and writing.

98 This is true, as learners' duration of language exposure affects their
99 learning outcomes when it comes to their language skills. As per
100 observation by the researchers, language input in poorer learning
101 environments results to low language acquisition and skills as learners
102 are not well-immersed in various language materials.

103
104 Another gap is seen on the interaction between teacher-learner
105 and learner-learner/s employing the English language during
106 assessments and performances in English classes. Thirunavukkarsu
107 (2015) confirmed that students actually like to use their daily language
108 to communicate with others and that they learn better when the
109 language used for instruction is a familiar language which they speak
110 in their daily activity. This is common in English classes of the
111 researcher herself when students asked permission to communicate in
112 Cebuano language. As observed, learners' native language, Cebuano,
113 is an ease to them when use in their oral or written communication.
114 However, as Domingo (2020) highlighted, problems usually emerge
115 when they need to communicate using the English language.

116
117 From the abovementioned problems in the secondary
118 educational context of using English as the medium of instruction, the
119 researcher proposed a theory to address the educational challenges on

120 using EMI in language classes. This study proposes a theory on
121 Instruction-Immersion-Interaction (3Is) Theory of English language
122 proficiency in secondary education. This is anchored on the existing
123 learning theories of Piaget's Cognitive Learning Theory, Skinner's
124 Behavioral Learning Theory and Vygotsky's Socio-cultural Learning
125 Theory. Additionally, this proposed theory also anchors the language
126 theories of Total Physical Response (TPR) and Communicative
127 Language Teaching (CLT).

128

129 The main objective of this study is to examine the effectiveness
130 of Instruction-Immersion-Interaction (3Is) Theory of English language
131 as the medium of instruction (EMI) in secondary education.
132 Furthermore, the specific objectives of the study are identified. First,
133 describe English language as the medium of instruction used by
134 educators and learners in English classes. Second, determine the
135 quality of learners' language exposure in varied contexts through EMI.
136 Third, assess the interaction between teacher-learner and
137 learner/learner/s employing the English language.

138

139

140

141 **RESEARCH METHODOLOGY**

142

143 This study utilized the Deductive Axiomatic Approach in Theory
144 Generation that followed the steps prescribed by Padua (2012). Axiom
145 is a statement which is regarded as being established, accepted, or
146 self-evidently true (Oxford Languages Dictionary). In this study, five
147 axioms are logically derived through the subsequent literature review.
148 Proposition is a statement that predicts a relationship between two or
149 more variables (Srivastava, 2023). These five axioms are examined
150 and then deduced into three emergent propositions.

151

152 According to Padua (2012), theory refers to a set of interrelated
153 constructs (concepts), definitions and propositions that presents a
154 systematic view of phenomena by specifying relations among
155 variables, with the purpose of explaining, predicting and controlling the
156 phenomena. From these three propositions, Instruction-
157 ImmersionInteraction (3 Is) Theory of English Language Proficiency in
158 Secondary Education is formulated. This theory aims to address the
159 educational challenges on using EMI in English language classes.

160

161 Theory generation has processes to be taken systematically. The
162 processes of building the said theory are organized and enumerated
163 below based on Padua's Deductive Axiomatic Approach in Theory
164 Development.

165

166

167

168 *Figure 1:*

169 *Deductive Axiomatic Approach in Theory Development (Padua, 2012)*

170

171

172 **Choosing the Phenomenon of Interest**

173

174 This is the first step in theory generation following the deductive
175 axiomatic approach. A phenomenon is a general result that has been
176 observed reliably in research (Price, et al., 2020). It is necessary to
177 focus on selecting the specific area or field of study within the
178 educational context where the theory has to be developed. As
179 highlighted by Ven (2016), research phenomenon can be any problem,
180 issue, or topic that is chosen as the subject of an investigation. The
181 phenomenon may originate in either the practical world of affairs, a
182 theoretical discipline, or a personal experience or insight. It may be
183 perceived to represent an unsatisfying circumstance, a promising
184 opportunity or simply a topic of interest.

185

186 This step is the primary focus as the researcher herself observed
187 problems in the utilization of English as a medium of instruction in
188 secondary English language classes. These problems are the
189 phenomena that interest her as these are challenging and brought
190 impact to education. As defined by InfoSciPedia (2022), Phenomenon
191 of Interest is the main situation that you are observing and interested in
192 studying. According to Ahmed, et al., (2023), there is an impact of EMI
193 on students' academic achievement however, EMI has potential
194 negative impact linguistic identity development of non-native English
195 speakers. With those said, the researcher wanted to address the gap
196 in employing English language in secondary education. Weick (1992)
197 underscored that theory-driven research is essential when grounding
198 the research phenomenon as all theories are about practice and
199 practicality, and the trick is to discover those settings and conditions
200 under which they hold true.

201

202 **Reading the Literature**

203

204 Having chosen English language teaching in secondary
205 education as the phenomenon of interest in this study, the next
206 essential process is reading related literature expansively. According to
207 the Writing Resources of University of Illinois, the purpose of a
208 literature review is to collect relevant, timely research on your chosen
209 topic, and synthesize it into a cohesive summary of existing knowledge
210 in the field. It allows researcher to gain familiarity with the current
211 knowledge in the chosen field, as well as the boundaries and limitations
212 of that field. Reading various literature provided the researcher with
213 comprehensive understanding of existing researches. These existing
214 literature ensured that the focus of the study remained grounded in the
215 secondary educational contexts. Literature that are interesting are
216 those that are relevant to the implications and challenges in the field of
217 English language teaching.

218

219 Literature included in this study encompassed the function of
220 EMI globally and nationally in education, the gaps on employing EMI
221 in language classes for both teachers and learners and the existing
222 theories to which this proposed theory is similar of and differs on.
223 Through the thorough reading and understanding of the different
224 literature, the researcher summarized them to create the five axioms.

225 Literature reviews also help the researcher gain an understanding of
226 the theory driving the field of English language teaching employing EMI.

227

228 **Brainstorming**

229

230 Brainstorming as the next step in this theory generation
231 encouraged the researcher for creative thinking and generated diverse
232 ideas that led to the exploration of the varied perspectives on the
233 utilization of EMI in ELT. Brainstorming is a helpful way to generate
234 ideas at any stage of the process, whether you're trying to come up with
235 a general topic before you begin your research, narrowing your focus
236 or deciding what support to use for a certain paragraph (Writers' Center,
237 Eastern Washington University, 2024).

238

239 In this study, brainstorming of ideas came from her coeducators,
240 students who are now professionals and professors serving as
241 resources in support to this proposed theory. The world is too rich and
242 multi-layered to be captured adequately by any single person. It
243 requires a researcher to be reflexive (Alvesson & Skoldberg, 2000) and
244 recognize his/her perspective, and to obtain and coordinate
245 perspectives of other key stakeholders in order to identify robust
246 features of the phenomenon being studied. Brainstorming enabled the
247 researcher to edit and update this study as it should be in accordance
248 to its research objectives.

249

250 **Formulating the Assumptions (Axioms) and Propositions**

251

252 Desired outcomes from this study basically came from the five
253 axioms derived from diverse literature. The existing literature were the
254 basis for the axioms to be developed which also supported the axioms
255 themselves. These five axioms formulated were then deduced to form
256 the three propositions. Thus, the Deductive Axiomatic Approach in
257 Theory Development is used (Padua, 2012). Propositions as defined
258 by Paul (2020), are statements concerned with the relationships among
259 concepts. The researcher scrutinized and elaborated the three
260 propositions as proposal to the problem. These propositions formulated
261 were studied and presented logically as having the justification from the
262 specific axioms. Since a theory is a coherent explanation or
263 interpretation of one or more phenomena (Price, et al., 2020), from the
264 three propositions, the theory on EMI, had to be created.

265

266 **Theory Construction**

267

268 Paul (2020) defined theory building as the means by which
269 researchers hope to achieve the research purpose. The last step of
270 theory development is supported by Padua (2012) stating that, one of
271 the forms of a theory is the Axiomatic Form. This defines theory as a
272 set of interrelated propositions and definitions derived from axioms,
273 thus, this is the deductive form of a theory. The proposed theory was
274 generated using an axiomatic approach where in the researcher
275 analyzed the propositions developed. From the three propositions, Paul
276 (2020), strengthened that the primary goal of theory is to understand
277 the relationships among various phenomena in which the theory
278 provided linkages among different concepts. One of the functions of a
279 theory is for Prediction. It proposes the occurrence of a future event
280 (Padua, 2012).

281

282 From the three propositions, it is theorized that English as a
283 Medium of Instruction (EMI) should be used in the language
284 classes of secondary education to address educational challenges
285 among learners. From this theorization, the most accurate vocabulary
286 to solve each proposition is rationally stated. Hence, the first proposition
287 is to be addressed through Instruction, the second proposition is to be
288 solved through Immersion and the third proposition is best to be
289 answered though Interaction. Thus, this theory is developed and shall
290 be called Instruction-Immersion-Interaction (3 Is) Theory of English as
291 Medium of Instruction (EMI) in Secondary Education.

292

293

294 **LITERATURE**

295

296 The five (5) axioms are derived out of the literature used. They
297 are comprehensibly presented below.

298

299 **Axioms**

300

301 English as a medium of instruction (EMI) has been increasingly
302 implemented in schools globally, including in non-English-speaking
303 countries. This implementation aims to prepare students for the global
304 workforce and improve their proficiency in English as a lingua franca.

305 However, the effectiveness of EMI has been a widely debated topic in
306 education. EMI implementation varies depending on the context and
307 stakeholders involved. Factors to be considered include the teachers'
308 qualifications, students' language proficiency and curriculum design.
309 There is an impact of EMI on students' academic achievement,
310 language proficiency, and socio-cultural development. Implementing
311 EMI can result in improved language proficiency and academic
312 outcomes when appropriately designed and executed. However, there
313 are potential negative impact of EMI on the cultural and linguistic
314 identity development of non-native English speakers (Ahmed, et al.,
315 2023).

316

317 García (2019) examined teachers' and students' perceptions
318 towards the use of EMI. Teachers reported challenges in overcoming
319 the different levels of English language acquisition among students,
320 while students who participated in EMI teaching tended to feel more
321 confident in communicating in English. The employment of English as
322 a Medium of Instruction (EMI) made English as the primary language
323 for teaching academic subjects beyond the confines of language itself
324 (Johnson and Lee 2020). As English's dominance grew in international
325 contexts, educators and institutions began to recognize the potential for
326 harnessing this linguistic ubiquity to facilitate the learning of various
327 disciplines (Choi 2017).

328

329 There has been a spread of English as the dominant lingua
330 franca worldwide, its educational impact on language rights, and the
331 underlying tension between globalization and national identity. It uses
332 the public debates surrounding these events to critically explore the
333 legal, cultural and pedagogical issues endemic to English medium
334 instruction, but also to address deeper tensions between globalization
335 and linguistic diversity. Though recognizing the utility of English as a
336 common vehicle for global communication, it was concluded that the
337 "rise of global English" is not a zero-sum game, but rather demands
338 measured strategies that reasonably balance the competing interests
339 at stake and maintain a sense of proportionality (Salomone, 2015).

340

341 The adoption of EMI as a pedagogical approach is underpinned
342 by several compelling reasons. The globalized nature of the modern
343 world demands graduates who are not only academically proficient but
344 also possess the ability to communicate effectively across linguistic

345 borders (Kachru 2020). EMI addresses this imperative by creating an
346 immersive environment where learners are constantly exposed to and
347 compelled to engage with English, thereby nurturing their language
348 skills organically (Bruthiaux, 2018).

349

350 EMI has become a global phenomenon. Almost every country
351 of the world has adopted EMI in their classroom from primary to
352 university level. Educators in today's time are faced with the extreme
353 challenge of addressing the needs of the growing number of students
354 whose primary language (L1) is not English. In EMI context, since
355 learners are exposed to "language features in specific situational or
356 linguistic context over and over again, learners develop a stronger and
357 stronger network of 'connections' between these elements" (Lightbrown
358 and Spada, 2006: 41).

359

360 Language education has remarkably undergone a major shift
361 since the advent of the communicative approach in the 1970s. As
362 English has long become the world's lingua franca, the approach to its
363 teaching and learning has also witnessed an outstanding breakthrough.
364 This is illustrated by the growing figures of non-native English language
365 speakers that far exceed the native ones, and that entails a special
366 status for English. Therefore, different proposals have been made as to
367 how English should best be approached in teaching given its various
368 characteristics as an international language for communication. One of
369 these approaches is English as a medium of instruction (EMI). In this
370 regard, and in their attempt to attain internationalization and develop
371 the quality of many institutions in non-English speaking countries (e.g.,
372 Japan, China, Malaysia, Germany, etc.) have opted for the world's first
373 language as a means of instruction in various academic subjects,
374 namely the science-related ones (Elkhayma, 2022).

375

376 The EMI status in Asia is no less prominent than that of Europe.
377 Many Asian countries, particularly Singapore, Malaysia, Hong Kong,
378 etc. have had long traditions in implementing instructional English in
379 their education system. Since 1979 EMI has become the common
380 trend in almost all universities in the country. In 1987, Singapore
381 became one of the first countries in the world to use English as the
382 language of instruction in most school subjects. Malaysia, have decided
383 on English as a language of teaching and learning (Rigetetal, 2018).
384 China has premiered English as a teaching language in various

385 university subjects. Japan's most universities had already incorporated
386 English in their study programs and entrance examinations (Silver et
387 al., 2002). In the Middle East, similar efforts have been made to
388 increase the number of EMI programs in universities (Galloway, 2020).
389 Numerous benefits can be drawn from implementing English for
390 instructional purposes in non-English speaking countries. For students,
391 following Chapple (2015), it can be an opportunity to improve their
392 English proficiency. Hence, it could be derived from the literature above
393 that **English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) is used in different**
394 **countries.** (Axiom 1)

395

396 Although English as a medium of instruction (EMI) has grown
397 exponentially in recent years, many perceived needs and challenges
398 remain unaddressed. This study investigated what kinds of challenges
399 students experience when trying to study in an EMI context, and how
400 they view their needs. These are the challenges with understanding
401 technical vocabulary, lecturers' inadequate use of English, code
402 switching, the English preparatory-year curriculum, English language
403 skills and the lack of language support in EMI programs (Griffiths,
404 2017).

405

406 Moreover, a recent study by Lee (2021) compared academic test
407 results between EMI students and students taught in their native
408 language. The results showed that while EMI students showed
409 improvement in English, students who got instruction in their mother
410 tongue had better concept understanding in scientific subjects. In
411 general, these studies show that EMI has the potential to improve
412 students' English language acquisition and their ability to communicate
413 in the language. Nonetheless, challenges include understanding more
414 complex subject matter and potential gaps in native language
415 acquisition (Anggraini, 2023).

416

417 EMI (English-medium instruction) is defined by Dearden and
418 Macaro (2016) as providing instruction in English in contexts where
419 English is not the language commonly spoken. But these benefits are
420 accompanied by substantial challenges, perhaps the most notable of
421 which relates to students' language proficiency, as Belhiah and Elhami
422 (2015) report. After all, they need to read materials, listen to lectures,
423 and write often lengthy essays or theses in what they originally learned
424 as a foreign language (English) in a context where there is no intention

425 to give further instruction on the language itself (Griffiths, 2017). An
426 English medium education system is the one that uses English as the
427 primary medium of instruction. Manivannan (2006) explained that
428 because a working knowledge of English is perceived as being required
429 in many fields, professions, and occupations, many states throughout
430 the world mandate the teaching of English. Baloch (2003) reported that,
431 when English is considered as the medium of instruction it is directly
432 linked with the speaking competency of the teachers. These speaking
433 competencies include the teachers' fluency, vocabulary, grammar,
434 pronunciation, confidence for using English as medium of instruction. It
435 was highlighted that the teachers' competencies for using English as a
436 medium of instruction was described as deficient in grammar and
437 vocabulary, however average in fluency, pronunciation and confidence,
438 while speaking in English (Aziz, 2015).

439

440 English Medium Instruction (EMI) in secondary education has
441 increasingly become a focus of research. One dimension of this
442 research has been on whole-class interaction patterns of teachers and
443 students, interaction having been established as important for learning
444 in both second language (L2) contexts and in content subjects (Childs,
445 2021). Previous EMI studies have reported teacher dominance of the
446 interaction and low levels of student participation. A possible
447 explanation has been that research hitherto has investigated mostly
448 local EMI teachers who have been reported to lack the linguistic
449 proficiency to engage in 'unscripted' interaction. Thus, interaction was
450 similarly teacher dominated and students' responses were of low
451 linguistic complexity (An, 2021). This is further stated by Han (2023)
452 stating that in English Medium Instruction (EMI), one of the biggest
453 challenges is reportedly the teachers' own lack of English language
454 proficiency.

455

456 Formal instruction is one of the methods that ensures a very kind
457 of setting that takes learners through learning in a guided and
458 systematic way. This approach puts more emphasis on grammar,
459 vocabulary, and pronunciation in an explicit explanation and rules are
460 given to the learners. Such instruction is likely to be presented in a
461 sequenced and cumulative syllabus, presenting the material so that
462 there is the development of simpler to more complex. They stated that
463 such explicit instruction, which includes teaching the rules of grammar

464 and vocabulary, contributes a lot to the learners' proficiency (Porter &
465 Sofia, 2023).

466

467 In the Philippines, students and teachers favored using English
468 in instruction. Filipino students and teachers lucidly preferred for the
469 use of English in education because of the perceived usefulness of
470 English in development, learning, and communication. Moreover, code-
471 switching as coping mechanism was identified. This is the strategy
472 identified and characterized by the use of Filipino/Tagalog and Ilokano
473 during their classes. Teachers have difficulty in speaking fluent English,
474 eliciting interactions, and explaining lessons when using EMI. In so
475 doing, it was revealed that speaking English fluently is a challenge
476 being face by the teachers. As a challenge, teachers have the inability
477 to speak English fluently which is described as the lack of ability of
478 teachers to use straight or pure English during their classes (Azarias,
479 2022).

480

481 According to Schmidt's noticing hypothesis, if students do not
482 notice a particular structure, it may not be possible for him/her to learn
483 it. Consciousness-raising activities and explicit focus-on-form have a
484 crucial role in promoting L2 development (Fotos & Ellis, 1991; Long,
485 1991; Sharwood, 1993). Similarity, Lightbrown and Spada (2006:38)
486 agree on the importance of explicit focus-on-form by stating that
487 students may reach a point from which they fail to make further
488 progress on some features of the second language unless they also
489 have access to guided instruction". Based on this view, programs which
490 only focus on comprehension and fluency are likely to be less effective
491 in developing students' language skills (Capuso, 2019).

492

493 Using English as a medium of instruction is a practice employed
494 in many educational institutions worldwide. This approach involves
495 delivering academic content in the English language, regardless of the
496 student's native language. Many studies reveal mixed effects on
497 English proficiency, with gains in grammar and vocabulary but slower
498 oral fluency development. Challenges emerge as students struggle with
499 complex concepts in their non-native language, leading to increased
500 cognitive load and stress. Advocates argue using English as a medium
501 of instruction enhances educational quality. Critics counter that it favors
502 students from elite backgrounds, disadvantaging those with limited
503 English exposure. The synthesis emphasizes balancing language

504 acquisition benefits with equitable curriculum access, allowing students
505 to establish foundational knowledge in their native language before
506 transitioning to English for higher studies (Abdedaim, 2024).

507

508 Johnson (2020) points out that EMI teaching can result in
509 improved English proficiency, but there is also a possibility that students
510 have difficulty in understanding technical terms in English. Students
511 perceive EMI to be beneficial however, they face challenges related to
512 teachers' English proficiency, code-switching, vocabulary and receptive
513 as well as productive skills. They suggest that Englishproficient
514 educators' continuous use of English and language support from
515 teachers can help learners overcome these challenges effectively
516 (Sahito, et al., 2021). EMI implementation is still a concern for
517 educational researchers and educators in many countries in which
518 several challenges due to students' poor ability in English interaction,
519 vocabulary shortage, irrelevant course content, EMI lecturers'
520 pedagogical methods, and students' motivations for the use of EMI are
521 figured out (Bui, et al. 2023). Thus, the literature above generalizes that
522 **Language instruction challenges students' English proficiency.**
523 (Axiom 2)

524

525 Belhiah & Elhami (2014) identified several challenges related to
526 EMI, including content teachers' linguistic and pedagogic competence,
527 students' English language proficiency, and reading disciplinary content
528 in English. A review of the literature on EMI found that prior exposure
529 to EMI courses leads to improved academic outcomes. Despite the
530 growth of EMI, there is a lack of empirical research into its impact on
531 students' English learning and content absorption. Research suggests
532 that there are perceived advantages of an EMI education, such as
533 improved English language proficiency but it is important to consider
534 the specific context and the needs of the students when evaluating the
535 effectiveness of EMI in enhancing language proficiency.

536

537 Research showed that in some areas of language proficiency,
538 students in immersion programs outperformed their non-immersion
539 peers (Genesee, 1987). What actually distinguishes immersion
540 learning from the conventional classroom learning setup is that
541 immersion learning includes learners having to be exposed to the
542 practicalities of using the targeted language concerning its grammar,
543 vocabulary, and pronunciation. Such findings help explain the fact that,

544 while immersion learning will do much more in improving English
545 language capability, it will also suggest that such an experience
546 environment could be most useful for learners looking to acquire this
547 language effectively. In the case of an immersion environment, students
548 are placed in a surrounding of native speakers who give them the
549 genuine atmosphere in speaking the language (Cook, 2011).

550

551 More recently, Lyster and Collins (2010) pointed out that
552 students in an immersion setting develop the ability to communicate
553 and, in fact, relatively high levels of accuracy in the use of grammatical
554 structures. Immersion learning provides fluency and communicative
555 competence ensuring that besides gaining accuracy in the learning of
556 English language, learners also develop fluency. Immersion learning
557 presents the best opportunity different from formal instruction, whereby
558 learners find themselves in the company of native speakers, therefore
559 having the most authentic language experience (Cook, 2011).

560

561 Based on the connectionist theory, students are supposedly
562 developing their language skills as they are studying the content.
563 Krashen's input hypothesis can also provide an explanation for the
564 development of language skills as the result of exposure to the target
565 language. Krashen claims that "acquisition occurs when one is exposed
566 to language that is comprehensible. Exposure to meaningful input even
567 without explicit focus on the language can help students develop their
568 language. In contrast to the theories which support natural
569 development of language skills through exposure only, there are also
570 theories which claim a different view point.

571

572 Cheng et al. (2010) claimed that English immersion has a close
573 relation to students' achievement, cognitive development and teaching
574 and learning process concerning teacher education. A survey study by
575 Rios-Aguilar et al. (2012) revealed that there is an increased focus on
576 learners' English language development through immersion learning.
577 In case of English language immersion setting, the designed situation
578 will provide overwhelming language exposure or language learning
579 experiences in which second language learners get immersed in that
580 situation. In the English immersion environment, the learners are
581 guided and monitored by the teachers in various activities such as
582 telling stories and familiar routines to acquire better level of English
583 proficiency in both words, phrases, sentences, and texts as well.

584

585 English immersion education is a method in teaching English in
586 which the English language becomes the medium of instruction and
587 content taught to students (Jeon, 2012). Qiang & Siegel (2012) affirmed
588 that teaching English in English immersion setting concerns foreign
589 language acquisition and subject content learning. In the immersion
590 system, the acquisition of the target language is achieved by making
591 the language as the medium of instruction for subject content. To these
592 respects, Huang, Trube, and Yu (2011) explained that in the English
593 immersion program, English language learning is taught as meaningful
594 as possible addressing the daily life of the students and attract them to
595 use English in their everyday activities. A study by Poon (2016)
596 discovered that to provide learners get immersed in the English
597 environment, formal and informal learning of English are incorporated
598 into different domains and various activities such as courses, academic
599 experiences, field-observation, homestay, cultural visit, tours, and other
600 outdoor activities.

601

602 The immersion approach to second-language and literacy
603 development proved itself to be the most successful school-based
604 language program model available. English-proficient immersion
605 students typically achieve higher levels of minority (non-English)
606 language proficiency when compared with students in other types of
607 language programs. Immersion students who begin the program as
608 English speakers consistently develop native-like levels of
609 comprehension, such as listening and reading skills, in their second
610 language. They also display fluency and confidence when using it.
611 Further, the more time spent learning through the non-English
612 language, the higher the level of proficiency attained. English proficient
613 immersion students are capable of achieving as well as, and in some
614 cases better than, non-immersion peers on standardized measures of
615 reading (Fortune, 2019). Based from the literature exposed,
616 **Immersion to English language is linked to students' language**
617 **skills.** (Axiom 3)

618

619 "Interaction in the classroom" pertains to the dialogue that takes
620 place between instructors and students in addition to between all
621 students, during which the classmates' active involvement and
622 understanding become crucial. The socio-cultural activities that assist
623 learners in acquiring knowledge collectively include dialogues.

624 Educational talk, also known as "exploratory talk" and "presentational
625 talk," has been used to describe interactions that take place in the
626 classroom between and even among different parties (Mercer &
627 Dawes, 2008; Barnes, 2008).

628

629 Interaction has continued to be an effective method for improving
630 English language acquisition. In the classroom, interaction is still a
631 fundamental strategy that is frequently used to improve learning in ELT.
632 Numerous studies have shown a strong correlation between students'
633 performance in learning English as a second language and classroom
634 engagement strategies (Wang & Castro, 2010). According to the claims
635 of the interaction theory model, interaction and conversation in the
636 classroom can quickly boost the formation of intercultural interaction
637 (Long, 1984).

638

639 According to Mercer and Dawes (2008), oral and/or textual
640 interaction between students and teachers is extremely important.
641 Essentially, the concentration is on learners' participation in genuine
642 dialogue and integration of the principles learned via conversation
643 (Long & Robinson, 1998). According to the communicative paradigm,
644 L2 learning instruction is oriented on the needs of the learners, who
645 practice their linguistic skills by engaging in real-world interactions.

646

647 The importance of interaction in mastering the English language
648 cannot be overstated. This investigation seeks to interpret the
649 interaction as a process for foreign language classroom instruction. In
650 an ELT classroom, there are often three main forms of interaction:
651 Communication between the pupils and the teacher; Matching
652 Communication (Interplay with learners' companions who are seated
653 close to them or together with them), and Collaborative Conversations.
654 These encounters require the learners to participate in partnerships or
655 small - groups and expose participants to a variety of communication
656 techniques, including talks, demonstrations, ideation, group activities,
657 and more. Additionally, it requires learners to engage in comprehensive
658 discussions (Kumpulainen & Mutanen, 1998).

659

660 Poor comprehension develops in linguistic classes because of
661 the absence of interaction. Long (1984), who is often credited as the
662 creator of interactionism in English communicative education, claims
663 that a lack of interaction is to blame for the ELT class's poor progress

664 toward conversational proficiency in the language. To improve
665 communicative proficiency in language classes, several strategies are
666 used. The methods used to improve interactions include student
667 engagement, leadership, surveys, simulations, matching, evaluations,
668 and communicative language teaching (CLT). The Communicative
669 Strategy is currently being widely adopted by ELT to support English
670 language instruction, particularly in developing nations where English
671 has been studied as a foreign language.

672

673 Interactions have continued to be an essential component of
674 acquiring English as a foreign language. It was determined that
675 interaction will continue to be a fundamental strategy regularly used to
676 improve learning in English language teaching (ELT) classrooms.
677 Contact, particularly in the classroom, helps identify the actual
678 difficulties that students face when learning a second language. It has
679 been demonstrated that consistent engagement that directly involves
680 classmates throughout classroom activities prompts teachers to
681 respond quickly to use effective strategies for learners (Ahmad, et al.,
682 2023). According to the literature discussed, **Learners' social
683 interaction develops English communication.** (Axiom 4)

684

685 In an EMI context, the classroom learner, therefore, faces a dual
686 task of learning both the content and the language that encodes the
687 content, and instruction comes down to scaffolding a comprehension of
688 the meaning of the content and, at the same time, cultivating English
689 language proficiency (Han, 2023). To wit, both the instruction and the
690 learning revolve around processing and producing meaning (content)
691 and form (language) mappings, importantly, within a disciplinary
692 context.

693

694 The EMI approach needs to be approached with caution to
695 ensure that concept understanding is not overlooked in the effort to
696 improve students' English proficiency (Anggraini, 2023). Currently, the
697 world is seeing a boom in EMI as an educational model in universities,
698 secondary schools and even primary schools. There are effects of EMI
699 on language learning, content learning, teaching delivery, quality of
700 education, inequalities of access, language flexibility and hybridity, the
701 competencies needed to be a successful EMI teacher, and other
702 multifaceted aspects of EMI (EMI Oxford Research Group).

703

704 The issues on the adoption of EMI for students with different
705 levels of English proficiency, and different subjects have not been fully
706 addressed (Zhao and Dixon, 2020). Byun et al. (2018) argued that the
707 compulsory adoption of English-Medium Instruction (EMI) seems to
708 lack the much-needed support system. The quality of EMI programs
709 and the learning they might facilitate has often been overlooked (e.g.,
710 Aguilar 2017; He and Chiang 2016). Furthermore, global
711 inconsistencies in relation to EMI pre- and in-service linguistic and
712 pedagogic support exist (e.g., Macaro 2018), therefore, the overall
713 implementation of EMI across academic disciplines indicates that it can
714 hinder student's comprehension of the teaching content.

715

716 Nevertheless, learners could utilize English language through
717 instruction to address the challenges of students in enhancing
718 language proficiency. Han (2023) accentuated, promoting content
719 (instruction) and language learning in the same breath – is not only
720 desirable but also feasible. In the teaching and learning process, a
721 certain language as the medium of instruction plays a vital role in
722 ensuring success in the delivery of instruction. This has given birth to
723 various policies on what language should be used in teaching. One of
724 these policies is the use of English as Medium of Instruction (EMI). EMI
725 is characterized by the use of English in teaching academic course in
726 areas in which English is not the mother tongue of most population.
727 Furthermore, educators wanted English no matter what it cost their
728 students. Azarias (2022) accentuates the fact that EMI has been
729 perceived to be constructive to the student. In the lights of the
730 pedagogical challenges of using EMI, teachers and students were still
731 firmly convinced that the advantages and opportunities of teaching and
732 learning in English overshadowed the disadvantages.

733

734 Real exposure to the second language is maximized to the point
735 of fluency and communicative competence with immersion learning.
736 Since immersion learning is an authentic, naturalistic experience of the
737 language, it can prove beneficial toward language growth. Immersion
738 environment makes it possible to practice actual language use even
739 more often, and across far more contexts, than would be likely in a
740 nonimmersion environment. Balancing the explicit instruction of the
741 classroom with the immersive, context-rich experiences of language
742 use, may be the most all-encompassing way of looking at language
743 acquisition (Castillo and Porter, 2023). Knell et al. (2007) evaluated that

744 immersion students perform better on English vocabulary, word
 745 identification and oral proficiency. The language learners become
 746 proficient in the second language and increase cultural awareness
 747 while reaching a high level of academic achievement (Caldas &
 748 CaronCaldas, 2010; Ahn, 2015; Poon, 2016; Lee, 2009).

749

750 Interaction encourages open communication exposure, which speeds
 751 up students' acquisition of second language abilities in a short amount
 752 of time. Additionally, it aids in identifying the pupils' actual language
 753 acquisition difficulties. It pushes educators to quickly use effective
 754 strategies to instill behavioral modifications in their students. English
 755 language acquisition in the classroom benefits from the interaction. The
 756 majority of ELT courses in the twenty-first century are becoming
 757 increasingly dominated by peer-group interactions. In addition to
 758 teaching students a foreign language, modern curricula incorporate
 759 interpersonal, collective, commitment, and interpersonal interaction
 760 skills (Barnes & Todd, 1995). With the literature presented, **English**
 761 **language Instruction, Immersion and Interaction enhance**
 762 **English proficiency. (Axiom 5)**

763

764 *Figure 2:*
 765 *The Summary of Axioms and Propositions*

766

Axioms	Propositions		
1. English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) is used in different countries.	1. Implementing English as a medium of instruction in language classes addresses students' language skills.		
2. Language instruction challenges students' English proficiency.			
3. Immersion to English language is linked to students' language skills.		2. Language exposure to diverse contexts develops learners' English language skills.	
4. Learners' social interaction develops English communication.			3. Increased social interaction enhances learners' English language proficiency particularly in communication skills.
5. English language Instruction, Immersion and Interaction enhance English proficiency.			

767

768 **Development of Propositions**

769

770 The construction of the five axioms directed the researcher to
771 develop three propositions. These propositions are presented and
772 elaborated as follow:

773

774 **Proposition 1: Implementing English as a medium of instruction in**
775 **language classes addresses students' language skills.**

776

777 To justify this first proposition, a logical weaving of the Axioms 1 and 2
778 is stated as follow. English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) is used in
779 different countries. (*Axiom 1*) Language instruction challenges
780 students' English proficiency. (*Axiom 2*)

781

782 Based on the three fundamental truths (*Axioms 1 & 2*) as backed
783 up with the literature mentioned above, Proposition 1 proposes that
784 English as a medium of instruction in secondary education be
785 effectively utilized in language class instruction as it challenges
786 students' proficiency in English language. This focuses on the usage of
787 technical vocabulary, teacher expertise in actual teaching and attention
788 on diverse code-switching. As proposed, through Instruction, the
789 aforesaid educational challenges will be addressed as teachers will
790 model to the students the appropriateness of language use and give
791 comprehensive and comprehensible input on how English as the
792 language of instruction be used in English language classes may it be
793 oral or written communication.

794

795 **Proposition 2. Language exposure to diverse contexts develops**
796 **learners' English language skills.**

797

798 This second proposition is justified by the reasonable
799 combination of the Axioms 3 & 4 specified as follow. Immersion to
800 English language is linked to students' language skills. (*Axiom 3*)

801 Learners' social interaction develops English communication. (*Axiom 4*)

802

803 As the two general truths (*Axioms 3 & 4*) stated with the specific
804 support of the aforesaid literature, Proposition 2 proposes that English
805 as a medium of instruction in secondary education will develop
806 students' English language skills through Immersion on the varied
807 language contexts during English language classes. Through
808 Immersion, learners themselves are exposed to variety of experiential

809 activities using English language. Immersion focuses on ensuring
810 active exposure of language focusing on fluency, vocabulary and
811 grammar. These language competencies should be demonstrated first
812 by the teacher or authentic language materials should be presented to
813 the learners such as audio-visual of the native English speakers via
814 videos, movies, news reports, broadcasting, informative talks,
815 interviews, panel discussions, talk shows, animation, multimedia, vlogs,
816 podcast, etc. in relation to the lesson focused. These are all for the
817 learners' concrete and thorough learning leading to their English
818 language proficiency.

819

820 **Proposition 3. Increased social interaction enhances learners'**
821 **English language proficiency particularly in communication skills.**

822

823 The justification of this third proposition is having Axioms 4 and
824 5 reasonably combined. Learners' social interaction develops English
825 communication. (*Axiom 4*) English language Instruction, Immersion and
826 Interaction enhance English proficiency. (*Axiom 5*)

827

828 Presented with the two accepted truths (*Axioms 4 & 5*) with the
829 literature stated above, Proposition 3 proposes that English as a
830 medium of instruction in secondary education will enhance the English
831 language skills of the learners in the field of communication through
832 Interaction. Interaction could effectively be accomplished either teacher
833 to learner interaction or learner to learner/s interaction with the use of
834 English language orally. This approach aims to focus on teacher's
835 proficiency and enhancement of learners' language skills through the
836 interface of authentic assessments or performance tasks with the
837 teacher's guided instruction.

838

839 From above's three propositions derived from the three axioms,
840 Instruction-Immersion-Interaction (3Is) Theory of EMI aims to address
841 the aforesaid problems in secondary education pertaining to the use of
842 English language in language classes. Through Instruction, teachers
843 giving comprehensible use of language in teaching aids to learners'
844 comprehension and expression of their ideas in both written and oral
845 communication utilizing English language. By having students
846 immersed in diverse language contexts, they could be proficient in the
847 utilization of English language either or both written and oral

848 communication. The quality of interaction demonstrates the teacher's
849 proficiency and learners' language skills as the main concentrations.
850 These proposed solutions embody the theory of English Language
851 Proficiency in Secondary Education through Instruction-
852 ImmersionInteraction (3Is) Theory.

853

854

855 **Instruction-Immersion-Interaction (3 Is) Theory**

856

857 Instruction-Immersion-Interaction are the three non-sequential
858 approaches of English language learning utilizing English as a medium
859 of instruction. These ways could address the educational problems in
860 secondary English language classes specifically the gap between
861 educators and learners in using English language as the medium of
862 instruction in English classes; the gap on the quality of learners'
863 language exposure in diverse contexts through the utilization of English
864 as the medium of instruction; and the gap on the interaction between
865 teacher-learner and learner-learner/s employing the English language
866 during assessments and performances in English classes. EMI is about
867 developing the ability of the learners to communicate content in English.
868 Since communication is oral as well as written, EMI is about providing
869 conditions under which the learner can become skilled in both
870 comprehending and expressing ideas pertinent to the academic
871 subject, in English (Han, 2023).

872

873 This theory is in contrast to the structured curriculum-based
874 language instructions in the Department of Education. DepEd
875 mandated the sequential way of teaching English to students whereas
876 this 3 Is demonstrates that learning English doesn't have to be in a
877 sequence. Still a lot of English language students do not demonstrate
878 English proficiency by means of sequential approach. This claim is
879 strengthened by Han (2023) that, EMI is about creating conditions
880 conducive to content and language learning, about mitigating the
881 problem of lack of input generally plaguing EFL teaching, and about
882 boosting teachers' English language proficiency. Thus, it lies in doing
883 all of the above non-sequentially or simultaneously, rather than
884 sequentially as seen in current EMI models. DepEd is currently
885 following the EMI models of giving rich-input first before having students
886 immersed and interacted.

887

888 In this theory, learners could either utilize and learn English by
889 having immersion first or interaction. They could also learn English
890 through combination of any two of the 3Is. Learners learn English
891 during immersion as they are exposed to different language contexts
892 even without the instruction yet and they could even start with
893 interaction focusing on oral communication even without instruction yet
894 for as long as the directions and guidelines of each given task are
895 well explained and fully understood by the learners and in accordance
896 to the learner's learning styles and levels.

897

898 This theory explains that learning English does not always begin
899 with instruction and it doesn't mean that learners could not learn English
900 if they are directly immersed and or interacted communicatively with
901 teachers or other students. Consequently, 3Is is non-sequential. They
902 may be interchanged as long as English language is used as the
903 medium of learning English. This theory possibly predicts that
904 Instruction-Immersion-Interaction enhances learners' English
905 proficiency.

906

907 **Instruction** shows how the teachers use EMI in actual teaching.
908 This aims to address educational challenges in secondary education
909 language classes in terms of technical vocabulary, teacher proficiency
910 and code-switching diversity. As Protacio (2023) accentuated, teachers
911 believed in the inseparable link between the English language and the
912 lesson's contents since unconsciously, when students obtain the
913 meaning of the contents, they also acquire English. Vyomakesisri
914 (2017), meanwhile highlighted that learners strongly recognized
915 English as challenging to learn and that English language is not simple
916 to master with its grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, slang and
917 colloquialism, changes and sentence structure, and unfamiliarity with
918 connotative and denotative meanings of words are the key challenges
919 in English.

920

921 Particularly addressing the gap on the usage of technical
922 vocabulary, the researcher proposes that the teacher should use
923 vocabulary in English classes according to the learners' level. Easier
924 vocabularies are those that the students find familiar to them. In that
925 context, the teacher should start from where the learners are. This claim
926 is reinforced by Sun et al. (2016) that the total amount of school input
927 (instruction) significantly predicted English language outcomes in

928 relation to productive and receptive vocabulary and receptive grammar
929 skills. Whenever, learners are not acquainted of the vocabulary the
930 teacher utters, he could give synonym to it or use it in a simple and real-
931 life scenario sentences or last approach is the grammar translation
932 approach than proceeding throughout the instruction where learners
933 demonstrate difficulty comprehending the technical vocabulary.

934 Another concern in the use of EMI in the classroom is the teacher
935 expertise in actual teaching. As Peláez (2008) and Zlatić et al. (2014)
936 stress, teachers' essential and complex skills lie in communicative
937 competence. Teacher's communication skills affect the learners'
938 comprehension. Learners found it difficult if the teacher establishes
939 expertise in English language. Barnard (2018) claims that the rate
940 teachers speak significantly impacts how students perceive words. As
941 a result, it is critical to comprehend the speaking rate and adjust it
942 depending on the presented instruction. On the other hand, if the
943 teacher does not demonstrate expertise in language instruction,
944 learners would find it more difficult for them to comprehend and use
945 English language. As a proposal to this problem, the teacher should
946 know first the learners' language skills for him to adapt his
947 communicative competence. Learners should always be the center of
948 instruction.

949
950 Nevertheless, in the study of Karvonen (2017), she emphasized that
951 the main challenges of using English as the medium of instruction
952 include teachers' lack of proficiency both in the English language and
953 in teaching in English. She added that benefits can be achieved even if
954 English is taught as a second language as long as better materials and
955 curricula are developed in the local language. In disagreement to this,
956 this proposed theory states that English would be learned better by the
957 students if the teachers are proficient in using it throughout the
958 instruction in both written and oral communication. Hence, teachers
959 should learn the English language and literacy in critical and
960 empowering ways to teach English (National Council of Teachers of
961 English [NATE], 2015; Reddy et al., 2016). It has been stressed that
962 learning English can be done in a classroom setting (Ferdous, 2013).

963
964 The last problem to be addressed in Proposition 1 is
965 codeswitching diversity in using EMI in English language classes. As
966 defined by Merriam dictionary, Code-Switching is the practice of
967 alternating between two or more languages or varieties of language in

968 conversation. Most frequent languages being code-switched from
969 English language involve Filipino and Cebuano languages.
970 Nevertheless, the study of Domingo (2016) shows that students have
971 a positive attitude toward using English and Filipino or code-mixed
972 procedures in teaching. Smolicz et al. (2011) underscores the need to
973 learn English, Filipino and native tongues in which these languages
974 must complement, not exclude, each other. To solve this, the teacher
975 should model to her students the accurate use of English language in
976 language class and encourage them to do the same. Some of the
977 techniques in minimizing code-switching is presenting videos or movies
978 to the learners utilizing English language or with subtitles presented.

979

980 According to **Cognitive Learning Theory**, learning can be
981 explained as deep, complex, psychological phenomena such as
982 motivation, schemas and processes for learning (Bruner, 1996; Piaget,
983 1974). Teaching occurs in phases with gradual complexity. Through
984 Instruction, learners are motivated by the teachers through the varied,
985 motivational language activities and learning the language starts from
986 easier to complex ones. This approach is related to the DepEd
987 recommendation to educators that there should be instruction of
988 learning from lower thinking skills and gradually proceeding to higher
989 thinking skills depending on the students' levels and preferences.
990 Another viewpoint is conceptual, which can be linked to both "Piaget's
991 developmental theory" and cognitive psychology in general. The
992 cognitive view on learning emphasizes the person's mental activity, the
993 growth of thought, cognitive techniques, and their use. The cognitive
994 approach views contact in English language teaching as aiding the
995 creation of the person's cognition since it aids in the activation of the
996 person's background experience. Since the arrangement of thought in
997 speech aids in the reconstruction of information, social contact is
998 considered as aiding a person to comprehend while becoming
999 knowledgeable of mental abilities. (Ahmad, et al., 2023)

1000

1001 In the learning dimension, the teachers strongly agreed that
1002 English Language Instruction (ELI) improves language proficiency and
1003 supports possibilities for improvement and self-confidence. For them,
1004 English is a learning booster. Chou (2018) believes that
1005 comprehensible input integrates unfamiliar linguistic material (e.g.,
1006 words and phrases) efficiently with familiar ones, making the received
1007 information more challenging to comprehend. It indicates that

1008 comprehensible input gives learners sufficient prior knowledge to
1009 comprehend and interpret language clues. EMI appears to be
1010 advantageous for learners in terms of academic achievement as well
1011 as in enhancing English proficiency (Galloway, et al, 2017; Rogier,
1012 2012; Rose et al., 2020; Sahan & Sahan, 2021).

1013

1014 Similarly, Sniad (2016) emphasizes that input relates to what the
1015 language learners are exposed to whether written or spoken. It is what
1016 they hear and seen in the target language around them. The use of
1017 pictures, signs, gestures, repetition and a simplified vocabulary and
1018 grammar structure are all proposed as elements that contribute to the
1019 comprehension of the material. It enables the teacher to communicate
1020 the information meaningfully in English. Hence, teaching the topics
1021 needs the teacher's knowledge and abilities in English (Protacio, 2023).
1022 As Noviyante (2017) mentioned, EMI is used to give instruction, confirm
1023 the students' understanding and give feedback.

1024

1025 **Immersion** demonstrates how learners are immersed in
1026 different language contexts through EMI. Its objective is to ensure an
1027 effective exposure of language to learners along with the teachers'
1028 language proficiency, specifically fluency, vocabulary and grammar.
1029 Exposure to language can be defined as the contact that the learners
1030 have with the target language that they are attempting to learn. Practice
1031 and exposure to the English language are critical components of
1032 mastery (Protacio, 2023). English improves students' learning
1033 experience and proficiency, according to Ebad (2014), who researched
1034 the roles and functions of English as a medium of teaching. This is
1035 confirmed by Samer and Zoubi (2018) that there is a positive
1036 relationship between exposure to English language and language
1037 acquisition and its relationship to language skills.

1038

1039 To elaborate Proposition 2, the language materials the teacher
1040 exposes to the learners should be in accordance to their learning styles,
1041 should be engaging, should cater their language needs and should
1042 encourage students to act upon them critically, creatively and
1043 systematically. To support this proposal, Cunningsworth (1995)
1044 emphasized the role of instructional materials in language learning: a
1045 source of motivation and ideas for classroom activities, a reference
1046 source for students on grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, etc., a
1047 source of activities for learner practice and communicative interaction

1048 and a resource to present materials (spoken and written). These roles
1049 of language materials using EMI in classroom could aid to learners'
1050 effective language exposure which could lead to their meaningful social
1051 interaction through communication.

1052

1053 Additionally, for Immersion to be effective in English language
1054 classroom, the teachers should first recognize individual differences of
1055 their learners for the operative differentiated language engagement to
1056 be provided to them. Learners vary in their learning styles. One of the
1057 most popular models to explain learning styles is the VARK model,
1058 created by a New Zealand teacher, Neil Fleming. The subsections of
1059 the VARK model are: Visual, Aural, Read/Write and Kinesthetic.

1060 Visual – these learners learn best by seeing, responding to visual
1061 cues like images, graphs or charts. They might be distracted by seeing
1062 things outside. Aural -- these learners learn best by hearing, responding
1063 to auditory cues like verbal instruction, discussions or songs. They
1064 might be distracted by outside noises. Read/Write -- this is sometimes
1065 listed as a subsection of the visual category, but the VARK model puts
1066 it in its own category. These learners learn best by reading and writing,
1067 responding to written cues like lecture notes, books and cue cards.
1068 They might be distracted by poorly worded text, or text that doesn't
1069 match speech. Kinesthetic -- these learners learn best by doing,
1070 responding to tactile cues like movement, actions and real-life
1071 examples. They might be distracted by uncomfortable seats or room
1072 temperatures.

1073

1074 From these learning styles, the teacher should value learner's
1075 preferences in order to effectively immerse them into the suitable
1076 language materials. This claim is supported by Babayev (2021),
1077 underscoring that the teachers should pay a considerable attention to
1078 the content and design of instructional materials in order to involve the
1079 students who are going to take advantage of them. Through Immersion,
1080 the teacher should be equipped in using IMs that support language
1081 learning. Aside from textbooks that can provide valid, valuable, and
1082 self-regulated sources for learners, the emergence of online resources
1083 for English language learning has created opportunities for authentic
1084 language use. Huda, et al., (2023) mentions the access to authentic
1085 materials such as articles, videos, and podcasts exposing learners to
1086 real-life language usage, improving listening, reading, and
1087 comprehension skills. Bringing 'realia' into the classroom is one of the

1088 most effective ways to create an enjoyable class atmosphere and
1089 acquire the target language efficiently (Bala, 2015). Gee (2007)
1090 recognizes that there are language learning benefits for students who
1091 engage in playing interactive games simultaneously. It is necessary for
1092 teachers to receive education in implementing interactive games in the
1093 language classroom (Cowie and Khatibi, 2013).

1094

1095 In addition, the instructional materials in supporting language
1096 learning should be diverse for the learners' effective language
1097 Immersion. Realia or Visualizations immerse learners in cultural
1098 contexts, promoting authentic language acquisition through real-world
1099 applications. Games or interactive resources support language learning
1100 by engaging learners actively, promoting retention through practical
1101 application of vocabulary and grammar. Printed Materials include
1102 textbooks that provide learners with structured grammar and
1103 vocabulary lessons that are essential for foundational language
1104 learning. Digital resources offer interactive experiences and access to
1105 authentic language use, improving practical skills and engagement of
1106 the students.

1107

1108 Samer and Zoubi (2018) accentuated that one of the most
1109 central roles of the teacher is to provide learners with sufficient
1110 engagement to practice English language in a variety of contexts and
1111 from different speakers where the teachers can give practical examples
1112 of language, moreover they can apply natural input from television,
1113 cassettes, video, websites, books, and magazines. Tomasello (2003)
1114 strengthened this claim stressing that learners in input-rich
1115 environments with more frequent exposure to English input reach
1116 higher levels of English proficiency in language skills such as listening
1117 comprehension when compared to learners in input poorer
1118 environments. Several studies have been made on the impact of
1119 language exposure to the learning of the target language, and results
1120 agree that quality immersion to the target language improves language
1121 learning (Peregoy & Boyle, 2005).

1122

1123 **Behavioral Learning Theory** views learning as a response to
1124 stimuli in the environment where in the learner can manipulate, observe
1125 and described (Brown, 1994; Gass & Selinker, 1994; Skinner, 1957).
1126 Teaching thus is through practice, repetition, and rewards. Behaviorist
1127 influences in second language teaching can be observed in methods

1128 such as audio-lingual approach and situational language teaching
1129 (Lavadenz, 2011). Similarly, Immersion is having the learners actively
1130 involved to diverse language materials and language contexts. May it
1131 be written or oral form of communication, the learners respond to the
1132 language engagement they are encouraged to be engaged on. This is
1133 affirmed by the recommendation based on the findings of Samer and
1134 Zoubi (2018) that students should be continually exposed to the English
1135 language through watching English movies and program, surfing the
1136 internet, listening to radio, reading English books, magazines,
1137 newspapers, and practicing English language with native speakers on
1138 a daily basis. This encouraged them in overcoming their weaknesses
1139 and improving their fluency as well as proficiency in acquiring English
1140 language because massive amount is communicated in English.

1141

1142 Ramírez-Ortiz and Artunduaga-Cuéllar (2018) point out that
1143 students should be actively involved and engaged during the
1144 implementation of language tasks. It happens when students are
1145 encouraged and supported by their partners, gradually gain confidence,
1146 and start playing a more active role in speaking activities in English
1147 classes. Additionally, Faez (2012) stresses that teachers must establish
1148 a special relationship with diverse students regarding the use of
1149 English. According to Kristiawan (2013), English language usage must
1150 be maximized in students' cooperation and collaboration with their
1151 peers during language immersion. Demmert (2011) emphasizes the
1152 importance of considering cultural heritage when employing EMI. It
1153 should cater to the academic demands of all students, regardless of
1154 their personal background. Teachers must employ activities and
1155 examples relevant to their students' culture.

1156

1157 Immersion is associated to the language theory known as **Total**
1158 **Physical Response (TPR)** developed by James Asher (1977) in which
1159 it follows a gradually more complex sequence of grammatical structures
1160 enacted by the teacher's use of verbal commands and the learners' role
1161 is to physically respond to the commands. It differs in this proposed
1162 theory because through **Immersion**, learners are immersed in gradual
1163 complexity of diverse language materials but not just on grammar, it
1164 incorporates their exposure on fluency and vocabulary using English
1165 language. Grammar teaching starts from the basic ones before
1166 integrating to text structure. This is also true in vocabulary, as learners
1167 need to be immersed first in the basic words before using them in

1168 sentence construction. Furthermore, fluency has to begin with the basic
1169 sounds before reading them fluently as embedded in vocabulary,
1170 sentences and paragraphs.

1171

1172 **Interaction** establishes teacher-learner or learner-learner/s
1173 interface using English language. This has the aim to focus on teacher's
1174 proficiency and enhance learners' language skills highlighting linguistic
1175 exposure (that includes authentic assessments and performance tasks)
1176 and guided instruction. Case (2013) emphasizes that while the English
1177 language can assist students in sharing their personal experiences,
1178 teachers must provide proper guidance during the communication
1179 based on the language contexts. Teachers are encouraged to use
1180 authentic tasks in the classroom to involve students in meaningful
1181 learning to foster oral production.

1182

1183 To elucidate Proposition 3, there are possible authentic activities
1184 for Interaction. These include oral presentation, character portrayal,
1185 informative talk, role play or dramatization, broadcasting, hosting,
1186 interview, multimedia presentation, emceeing, talk show, panel
1187 discussion, picture analysis, news report, oral test, oral recitation,
1188 debate, poetry recital, among others. A student must be familiar with
1189 the English language's structure and how these components are
1190 utilized for communicating and interacting with others (Protacio, 2023).
1191 It is considered an advantage for speakers if they know a language
1192 other than their native language especially that in the present time,
1193 learning to use English language in communication benefits an
1194 individual (Domingo,2020). With the continuous improvement of
1195 English teaching way, the interaction and communication way in
1196 English teaching has become an important means to improve English
1197 teaching. The interaction and communication between teachers and
1198 students is helpful for the teachers to understand Basic English level of
1199 the students and student learning ability. (Li, 2016).

1200

1201 The main focus of Interaction is for learners' active linguistic
1202 exposure through authentic assessment and teacher's guided
1203 instruction in the English language environment. Here, communication
1204 utilizing English language is the ultimate goal of the teacher to assess
1205 learners' learning from language instruction and language immersion.
1206 Given the assigned performance tasks, learners can interact either
1207 integrating his or her knowledge socially, culturally or historically. Either

1208 of these three, the learners can interact though not as effective as they
1209 are in the use of English but they do learn through social interactions.
1210 Students must demonstrate that they can communicate effectively
1211 enough to complete a real-world assignment (Frias, 2014) – that is
1212 communicating using the English language. There is a value of
1213 interactions in English language classroom instruction. An instance of
1214 these perspectives is the socio-cultural interactionism viewpoint on
1215 acquiring the English language, which is typically linked with Vygotsky
1216 (1978). The viewpoint places special emphasis on the function of in the
1217 setting of engagement.

1218

1219 **Socio-cultural Learning Theory** highlights that learning is
1220 influenced by social, cultural and historical factors. Learning takes
1221 place within social interactions (Vygotsky's, 1978; Wertsch, 1991).
1222 There is a premise that second language teaching and learning take
1223 place within the social interactions of learners and more capable they
1224 seek to understand the cultural and historical influences on learning
1225 (Faltis & Hudelson, 1998; Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wertsch, 1991).
1226 Teaching occurs through meaningful interactions between experts and
1227 novices. English language acquisition is greatly influenced by the
1228 interactions between teachers and pupils. There is a propensity for
1229 learners speaking English as a foreign language to transmit some
1230 sociocultural elements, which might affect how they interact. As a result,
1231 classroom contact is frequently seen, especially when it occurs during
1232 a teaching session.

1233

1234 In the same way, Interaction between and among teacher and
1235 students vary on their level of language proficiency as this calls for oral
1236 communication. Interaction is still a fundamental strategy regularly
1237 used to accentuate understanding inside English language teaching
1238 (ELT) classrooms. It helps identify the actual difficulties that students
1239 face when learning a second language. Conversation plays a huge role
1240 in the acquisition of English as a foreign language by promoting
1241 conversations and interactions within the classroom. Interactional
1242 views of language are those that view language as the means to
1243 achieve relationships and performances (internal/innate features)
1244 between people (Richards & Rodgers, 1998, p. 17). There is at least
1245 some correspondence between interactional views of language and
1246 sociocultural views of learning (Lavadenz, 2011).

1247

1248 Shen (2013) stresses how students talk smoothly but with
1249 numerous mistakes. Meanwhile, some students talk slowly yet
1250 accurately. Balancing correctness and fluency in English classroom
1251 instruction is recommended to minimize language difficulties. Ajitha and
1252 Sivaranjani (2016) assert that English empowers students by providing
1253 global communication. It only implies that regular practice of English
1254 improves language proficiency in listening, speaking, reading, and
1255 writing. Domingo (2020) agreed that the learners' exposure to the target
1256 language does have impact in language learning in which students are
1257 exposed most to the English language when they are at school or with
1258 the use of different media compared to when they are at home or
1259 communicating with friends.

1260

1261 It should be emphasized that exposure can directly improve a
1262 target language so that language proficiency may be a result of social
1263 interaction with speakers of the target language (Peregoy & Boyle,
1264 2005). Extending the work on the role of interaction in SLA, Macaro,
1265 Graham and Woore (2016) further highlighted substantial student turns
1266 as a principle of high-quality interaction for second language learning
1267 in language classrooms. In addition, De Wilde et al. (2020) observed
1268 that learners made very large gains in overall language proficiency by
1269 means of their contact with English mainly speaking English. As
1270 highlighted by Beare (2018), "students can learn to speak English by
1271 speaking English itself."

1272

1273 English can enhance students' personalities. How a person
1274 communicates in English builds a good impression and delineates a
1275 character. Meanwhile, the teachers also agreed that the speed of
1276 speaking English should match students' level and that English should
1277 be used in social interactions (Protacio, 2023). As supported by
1278 Domingo (2020), language is a critical tool in communication and it
1279 cannot be denied that a good speaker of a language can communicate
1280 ideas to others through interaction. There is a significance between
1281 communication and the thought processes required while speaking to
1282 another speaker (Lantolf, 2000). Speaking is another way that the
1283 learning process may take shape; this is known as talking-assisted
1284 learning. In this manner, students might work with a partner to jointly
1285 develop knowledge (Lightbown & Spada, 2006). Discussions among
1286 participants in a group then clarify how language acquisition occurs
1287 through communication.

1288

1289 Interaction is also related to the language theory known as
1290 **Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)** through which the
1291 theorists Wilkens (1972), Halliday (1975) and Hymes (1967/1974)
1292 stated that CLT focuses on learning language to communicative
1293 notions, thus, communication is the ultimate goal of language learning
1294 which is achieved through interaction with others. Interactions are said
1295 to possess a significant impact on linguistic proficiency and linguistic
1296 development, according to contemporary ELT models on learning a
1297 foreign language for instance the "Interactions Hypothesis" and
1298 "Communicative Language Teaching Approach," etc. Language
1299 classroom interactions are crucial because they allow learners to
1300 participate in social activities that help them improve their interpersonal
1301 abilities as well as their self-confidence and sense of self-esteem as
1302 proficient linguistic communicators (Luk & Lin, 2007).

1303

1304 Nevertheless, it differs on the focus of four skills of language as
1305 **Interaction** deals mainly on developing speaking and listening as it
1306 focuses more on oral communication unlike CLT that it includes writing
1307 and reading skills. The employment of speaking skills in interpersonal
1308 interactions, according to the interaction model, greatly facilitates
1309 language learning. Listening comprehension is critical for learning
1310 language, according to the Interaction Hypothesis, which is similar to
1311 Krashen's Input Hypothesis. Besides, CLT is classified as following to
1312 the interactionist theory of learning and is now considered to be
1313 essential for effective second language teaching (Lavadenz, 2011).

1314

1315 Thoms (2012) summarized, in sociocultural theoretical view, the
1316 major aspects of language are tied and formed by the strategies in
1317 which people interact with others in various communicative contexts.
1318 He also added that language learners develop their competences in
1319 social interactions and relationships via participation in communication
1320 with more experienced, knowledgeable, and competent participants,
1321 such as teacher and/or peer (Thoms, 2012). The roles of teachers
1322 and/or peer in foreign language classroom are to guide and assist in
1323 completing linguistic tasks and language production through
1324 interaction. Classroom interaction involves teacher and students as
1325 interactants in using target language. In the classroom, communication
1326 is mostly initiated and maintained by the teachers. They, as a key holder
1327 of classroom communication, play prominent roles to manage the

1328 classroom participation. Moreover, social-cultural learning theory, as
1329 presented by Vygotsky (1962; 1978), serves to bring social interaction
1330 in L2 acquisition (Porter and Sofia, 2023).

1331

1332 The above mentioned are the related literature that both affirm
1333 and negate the proposed theory. Existing theories discussed above
1334 comprise the learning theories with their specific implications to
1335 teaching. Instruction is supported by Piaget's Cognitive Learning
1336 Theory, Immersion is supported by Skinner's Behavioral Learning
1337 Theory and Interaction is supported by Vygotsky's Socio-cultural
1338 Learning Theory.

1339

1340 Moreover, language theories namely, Communicative Language
1341 Teaching (CLT) and Total Physical Response (TPR) with similarities
1342 and differences to the proposed theory are hereby presented. As
1343 Lavadenz (2011) highlighted, there are categories of language theories.
1344 Instruction falls under Structural category (language is composed of
1345 interrelated linguistic forms) and Cognitive category (language is a
1346 biologically predetermined mental ability and that language learning
1347 primarily requires knowledge of the surface level of forms). Immersion
1348 falls under the Functional or Communicative category (language
1349 learning is a tool that is used to accomplish things or for certain
1350 purposes). Interaction falls under Interactional category (language is a
1351 means through which exchanges, performances and human
1352 relationships are created and maintained).

1353

1354 English has multidimensional uses and has significant value in
1355 education, language proficiency, professionalism, cultural
1356 development, language repertoire, and personal empowerment. This
1357 point is underlined by Alenezi (2010) stating that the selection of the
1358 EMI is a vital decision for the academe. Educational board imposed
1359 language education policies in a centralized education system for
1360 academic institutions. Such decisions impact teachers' competence
1361 and students' holistic development.

1362

1363 For the teachers, the state of utilizing English revealed its
1364 superiority and strong recognition (Protacio, 2023). Based on some
1365 experts view as quoted by Noviyante (2017), EMI is the use of English
1366 by both students and teacher in teaching and learning English. It means
1367 that the teacher uses EMI to deliver the content, give feedback and

1368 confirm students' understanding while learners use EMI in
 1369 presentations, discussions and asking and answering questions. These
 1370 ways are embodied in the proposed theory where there is Instruction,
 1371 Immersion and Interaction.
 1372

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 1374
 1375 **Figure 3:**
 1376 *The Proposed Instruction-Immersion-Interaction (3Is) Theory*
 1377 The diagram presents the generated theory,
 1378 InstructionImmersion-Interaction (3 Is) Theory of English Language
 1379 Proficiency in Secondary Education. This developed theory from the set
 1380 of interrelated propositions could enhance learners' English language
 1381 competencies as they engage with diverse language contexts through
 1382 Instruction, Immersion and Interaction non-sequentially. These 3 Is
 1383 approach utilizes English as the medium of instruction in English
 1384 language environments that would contribute to the field of English
 1385 Language Teaching (ELT) in secondary education.
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